

AMERICAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (AJMRI)

ISSN: 2158-8155 (ONLINE), 2832-4854 (PRINT)

VOLUME 1 ISSUE 3 (2022)

Indexed in

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PUBLISHED BY: E-PALLI, DELAWARE, USA

Implementation of the Experiential Learning Courses of the College of Teacher Education and Arts and Sciences: An Assessment

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Article Information

Received: May 24, 2022

Accepted: July 02, 2022

Published: July 04, 2022

Keywords

Competence, Demonstration, Involvement, Practicum, Supervision

ABSTRACT

The Experiential Learning Courses (ELC) are indispensable components of the New Teacher Education Curriculum per CHED Memorandum Order No. 30 s., 2004. This is pursuant to the National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS), core of the Teacher Education and Development (TEDP) of the government. The researcher utilized descriptive research in here with the aid of an instrument on Practice Teaching used by the CTEAS Practice Teaching supervisors in evaluating the exposure of the pre-service students and the implementation of the Experiential Learning Courses (ELC). The instrument used were the accomplished evaluation rating sheets of the Practice Teachers for the first and second shifts during their deployment in the second semester from SY 2010 – 2011 to 2013 – 2014. These were accomplished by the cooperating teachers where the Practice Teachers were assigned. The instrument was composed of three parts namely; instructional competence, professional and personal characteristics, and punctuality and attendance. There were three sub-components of instructional competence namely lesson planning, learner's involvement, and school, home and community involvement. It was found out that the student teachers both for BEED and BSED are within the age expected of them to be completing for the tertiary level of education. Mostly were female and have a very satisfactory academic performance. Also, the performance of BEED and BSED student teachers in demonstration teaching is very satisfactory in instructional competence, professional and personal characteristics, and attendance and punctuality. And the BEED and BSED student teachers displayed difference in terms of professional and personal characteristics. Therefore, these results could be a baseline for future improvement of experiential learning courses.

INTRODUCTION

The Experiential Learning Courses (ELC) are indispensable components of the New Teacher Education Curriculum per CHED Memorandum Order No. 30 s., 2004. This is pursuant to the National Competency Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS), core of the Teacher Education and Development (TEDP) of the government (ELC Handbook, 2009).

The ELC are intended to provide students with actual learning experiences in which they can observe, verify, reflect on and practice the different components of the teaching-learning processes in a variety of authentic school settings. Such experiences which are built around mentoring will begin with field observation and will gradually intensify into participation until students undertake practice teaching which eventually lead them to their chosen careers.

Speaking of career, the experiential learning courses paved the way of future teachers. On the other hand, Krumboltz said as cited by Toews (2008) stated that indecision is desirable and sensible as it allows the opportunity for the individual to benefit from unplanned events. He added that people with curiosity to explore learning opportunities, persistence to deal with obstacles, flexibility to address a variety of circumstances and optimism to maximize benefits from unplanned events, are more likely to capitalize on chance events and turn serendipity to opportunity.

But to Holland (Villar, 2009) in his Theory of Career

Choice, he emphasized that in choosing a career, people prefer jobs where one can be around others who are like them. Individual searches for environment that will let him use his skills and abilities and express his attitudes and values while taking on enjoyable problems and roles. Moreover, Parsons (Villar, 2009) agreed that people perform best when they are in jobs best suited to their abilities. He developed the Talent-Matching Approach which was later turned into the Trait and Factor Theory of Occupational Choice. He stated that occupational decision making occurs when people have achieved an accurate understanding of their individual traits, a knowledge of jobs and the labor market, and rational and objective judgment about the relationship between their individual traits and the labor market. Although, there are already theories like the abovementioned, challenges in college life and unemployment are still inevitable to some people.

The adoption of National Career Assessment Examination (2014) in the Philippine educational system is one big step in addressing challenges in college life and career mismatch. NCAE is a test taken by high school students that determines their strengths in different career fields.

The teaching profession has been struggling to keep pace with the changes in society and the accompanying challenges of the technological world. With the notion that teacher education, which consists of the pre-service education teachers and the in-service teachers, has been

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unable to bridge the growing gap between the needs and expectations of learners and the knowledge and skill levels of both new and existing teachers. It has been initiated to advocate a greater formal partnership among the main stakeholders.

In the College, the one in-charge for the Experiential Learning Courses (ELC) particularly the Field Study Courses and Practice Teaching adopt similar scheme for the exposure of the teacher education graduating students. On the first semester, they have to undergo the lump Field Study Courses (FS 1-6) and thereby completing all the worksheets and other requirements in the field. The pre-service teachers have a half-day immersion on the selected cooperating schools nearby because they still have subjects in the College.

Objectives

The research aims to assess the performance of the practice teachers for the SY 2010 – 2014.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions

1. What is the profile of the student teacher in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 general weighted average?
2. What is the performance of the student teachers in demonstration teaching in terms of the following components:
 - 2.1 instructional competence;
 - 2.2 professional and personal characteristics; and
 - 2.3 punctuality, promptness and attendance?
3. Is there a significant difference in the performance of student teachers between the courses as revealed by the aforementioned indicators?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Experiential learning is a flexible instructional tool, adaptable to suit most courses (Wright, 2000). However, only a handful of teachers utilize this kind of strategy in their classrooms. This has been the subject of most studies in which tried to describe the connection of academic experience and the world of work. It was clarified whether short-term experiential learning reduces the drawbacks that may prevent instructors from using this instructional technique. It was also highlighted the comparison of the instructor and student perspectives on three types of short-term exercises: observations, participant-observations, and field trips. Moreover, it was found out that short-term experiential assignments reduce the logistical concerns involved in experiential exercises and increase the opportunities for analytical reflection, especially for instructors of smaller courses and for non-field trip activities. In large introductory lecture courses, additional steps to structure the reflection process can successfully alleviate many of the problems dealing with lack of analysis. Proper selection of exercises included and careful choices about their use in courses or units with sensitive subject matter will help increase the chance of positive learning outcomes. In the study of

Parilla & Hesser (1998), he found out that most sociology departments provide students with the opportunity to participate in an internship. Yet faculty members often remain skeptical about the academic rigor of such experience-based learning. In his paper, he argued that internship help students achieve the educational goals of most sociology programs. Internships provide students with an extended opportunity to apply the sociological perspective to a “real world” setting. They also enable students to improve their analytical skills and their ability to make use of “the sociological imagination”. Like any instructional method, professors must carefully plan and structure internships to ensure that they are effective. Whenever possible, internships should require: (1) careful site selection, (2) a detailed learning agreement or contract, (3) attendance in a concurrent seminar, and (4) a set of cumulative assignments or a portfolio for evaluation.

This was supported by the study of Grant et al. (1981) saying that instructors find ways of adopting strategies to bring it to personal level and have alive, complex, complex arguments to a simpler tone for the students to readily absorb and digest concepts. Speaking of strategies of teaching, a new trend of introducing experiential learning courses was on the verge of implementation. Advances in technology have forced several educational reforms which include the development of a new educational paradigm for online distance education (Strait and Sauer, 2004). In here, instructors become mentors and guide the students and new challenges have been addressed through effective distance teaching, online collaboration and cooperation.

Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum Order number 30 was promulgated for the purpose of rationalizing the undergraduate teacher education in the country to keep pace with the demands of global competitiveness. The said CMO is in accordance with the pertinent provisions of Republic Act 7722, known as the Higher Education Act of 1004. CMO 30 embodies the policies and standards for the undergraduate teacher education curriculum.

Article V, section 13 of CHED Memorandum Order 30 states that, “field stud courses are intended to provide students with practical learning experiences in which they observe, verify, reflect on, in actual school setting. The experiences will begin with field observation and gradually intensify until students undertake practice teaching”.

The Field Study Courses adheres to the Vygotskian principle of social construction of knowledge and that meaningful learning and construction of knowledge will occur if learners work hands – on in relevant settings and with the proper guidance. Complementary to Vygotsky’s theory is Albert Bandura’s Social Learning Theory. Bandura asserted that learning takes place not only through imitation but also observation. Recently, the Situated Learning Theory reiterated Vygotsky’s and Bandura’s views. It emphasized that knowledge needs to be presented in an authentic context and that settings and applications that would normally involve knowledge and

that learning requires social interaction and collaboration. The field study experience is geared towards exactly this, to give pre-service teachers the opportunity to learn through meaningful and systematic exposure in actual settings.

Another important theoretical basis of this field study experience is reflective education. John Dewey stressed the vital role that reflection played in the growth and development of teachers. Reflection allows the learner explore his/her experiences in order to arrive at new understandings or insights. It may be done individually or through sharing and discussion with others.

Observation in actual setting is meant for the Field Study students to train their senses to really focus on important details of the learning situation and perceive them with clarity and objectivity. It entails that student learn to differentiate making an observation and interpreting the observation. Analysis involves the use of critical thinking to break down the components of what was observed, orchestrated or organized. Further on it will also involve the ability to synthesize, to organize into a coherent pattern the salient points of what are has analyzed and learned. Reflection involves the past, the present and future of the field study student. In light of each field experience episode, the FS students reflect on relevant past experiences that might have affected their beliefs, values and attitudes about the learning. The student also reflect on how each episode is affecting their present thinking and finally how their learnings will impact on their future as teachers.

Table 1: Respondents of the Study

School Year	Course				Over-all (N =235)	
	BEED		BSED		f	%
	f	%	f	%		
SY2010-11	36	23.38	17	20.99	53	22.55
SY2011-12	32	20.78	16	19.75	85	36.17
SY2012-13	37	24.03	20	24.69	69	29.36
SY2013-14	49	31.82	28	34.57	28	11.91
Total	154	100.00	81	100.00	235	100.00

than the BSED from SY 2010 – 2011 to SY 2013 – 2014 specifically SY 2010 – 2011, there are 36 BEED and 17 BSED, SY 2011 – 2012 there are 32 BEED and 16 BSED, SY 2012 – 2013 there are 37 BEED and 20 BSED, SY 2013 – 2014 there are 49 BEED and 28 BSED.

The data above implies that there are more students who preferred to take BEED course than BSED because there are more elementary schools in locality and eventually there are more job opportunities for them.

Performance of Student Teachers in Experiential Learning Courses

The following tables present the performance of BEED and BSED student teachers in the Experiential Learning Courses during their practice teaching exposure for the SY 2010 – 2011 to SY 2013 – 2014. There are three (3) components of the instruments namely instructional

METHODS

The researcher utilized descriptive research with the aid of an instrument on Practice Teaching used by the CTEAS Practice Teaching supervisors in evaluating the exposure of the pre-service students and the implementation of the Experiential Learning Courses (ELC). The instrument used were the accomplished evaluation rating sheets of the Practice Teachers for the first and second shifts during their deployment in the second semester from SY 2010 – 2011 to 2013 – 2014. These were accomplished by the cooperating teachers where the Practice Teachers were assigned.

The instrument is composed of three parts namely; instructional competence, professional and personal characteristics, and punctuality and attendance. There are three subcomponents of instructional competence namely lesson planning, learner’s involvement, and school, home and community involvement.

The following statistical measures were used to analyze the obtained data:

1. Use of frequency counts, percentages and ranking in tabulating the profile of the graduate-respondents.
2. Computation of mean for the extent of influence of the different factors to employability and the problems and solutions will be utilized by the researcher.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After the data was gathered and treated, the following are the results and findings of the study. It can be gleaned from the table that there are more enrollees in the BEED

competence, personal and professional characteristics, and punctuality and attendance.

Instructional Competence

Table 3 presents the performance of BEED and BSED student teachers in terms of the classroom instructional competence during the Experiential Learning Courses, practice teaching aspect. From the table, it can be seen that there are three sub-components as to lesson planning, learner’s achievement, and school, home and community involvement where there are 16 performance indicators for first component, 2 for the next, and 4 for the last component.

For the performance of BEED, there is an overall weighted mean of 8.4 for the instructional competence with a verbal description of very satisfactory while BSED have an overall weighted mean of 8.8 and also described

Table 2: Profile of the Respondents of the Study

Profile	BEED		BSED		Over-all	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Age:	--	--	--	--	--	--
24 & above	26	16.90	16	19.80	42	17.90
21-23 yrs old	79	51.30	48	59.30	127	54.00
20 yrs old & below	49	31.80	17	21.00	66	28.10
Total	154	100.00	81	100.00	235	100.00
Sex:	--	--	--	--	--	--
Male	30	19.50	29	35.80	59	25.10
Female	124	80.50	52	64.20	176	74.90
Total	154	100.00	81	100.00	235	100.00
GWA:	--	--	--	--	--	--
below 1.71	25	16.20	28	34.60	53	22.60
1.71 to 2.05	98	63.60	48	59.30	146	62.10
above 2.05	31	20.10	5	6.20	36	15.30
Total	154	100.00	81	100.00	235	100.00
Mean	1.92		1.811		1.88	
sd	0.16		0.17		0.17	

as very satisfactory.

With this, it is implied that both BEED and BSED are exhibiting very satisfactory traits in lesson planning, managing learner's achievement and facilitating school,

home and community involvement. This is the result of the preparation and exposure made by the College for every student teacher.

Table 6: Ranking of the Problems Encountered by the BEED and BSED Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University of Calbayog City

Performance Indicator	BEED			BSED		
	WM	SD	Desc	WM	SD	Desc
A. Lesson Planning						
1. Formulates/adopts objectives of lesson plan	9	1.02	O	9.2	1	O
2. Selects content and prepares appropriate instructional materials/teaching aids	8.4	1.3	VS	8.3	1.2	VS
3. Selects teaching methods/strategies	8	1	VS	8	1	VS
4. Relates new lesson with previous knowledge/skills	8	1	VS	8	1	VS
5. Provides appropriate motivation	8.1	1.2	VS	7.9	1.4	VS
6. Present and develops lessons	10	0.3	O	9.8	0.6	O
7. Conveys ideas clearly	9.5	1.2	O	9.7	0.7	O
8. Utilizes the art of questioning to develop higher level of thinking	9.1	1.3	O	9.5	0.9	O
9. Ensures learner's participation	8.7	1.2	VS	8.7	1	VS
10. Address individual differences	8.1	0.9	VS	8.4	0.8	VS
11. Shows mastery of the subject matter	7.9	0.7	VS	8.2	0.6	VS
12. Evaluates learning outcomes/performance of learners	8	0.8	VS	8.1	0.5	VS
13. Assesses lesson to determine desired outcomes within the allotted time	8	0.9	VS	8.3	0.7	VS
14. Maintains clean and orderly classroom	8	0.9	VS	8.4	0.8	VS
15. Maintains classroom conducive to learning	8.4	1.2	VS	8.6	0.9	VS
16. Handles disciplinary problems with tact and good judgment	8.5	1.1	VS	8.5	0.9	VS
B. Learners' Achievement						
1. Improves learners' achievement	8.2	0.9	VS	8.4	0.8	VS
2. Conducts appropriate RRE activities	8.1	0.8	VS	8.4	0.8	VS
C. School, Home and Community Involvement						
1. Observes and participates homeroom PTA activities	8	0.7	VS	8.4	0.8	VS
2. Reports learners progress to parents/guardians	8.2	0.9	VS	8.3	0.7	VS

3. Participates in school/community projects, co-curricular activities and in civic organizations	8.4	1.1	VS	8.4	08	VS
4. Encourages involvement of parents and stakeholders in school programs and activities	8.5	1.1	VS	8.3	0.8	VS
Overall	8.4	0.55	O	8.8	0.44	O

Legend: 10 – 9 = Outstanding, 7 – 8 = Very Satisfactory, 5 – 6 = Satisfactory, 3 – 4 = Poor, 1- 2 = Needs Improvement

Professional and Personal Characteristics

Table 4 presents the performance in demonstration teaching of BEED and BSED in terms of professional and personal characteristics. It is described as 5 - outstanding being the highest and 1 – needs improvement. There are 10 performance indicators along this component which are as follows, decisiveness, honesty/integrity/dedication/resourcefulness, courtesy, human relations, leadership, stress tolerance, fairness/justice, proper attire/good grooming.

From the table, it can be seen that BEED has a total weighted mean of 7.9 described as very satisfactory and BSED with a weighted mean of 7.8 and described as very satisfactory also. With this, it implies that both BEED and BSED are showing very satisfactory personal and professional characteristics. They can be trusted for duties and responsibilities along their line

Punctuality and Attendance. Table 5 presents the performance in demonstration teaching of BEED and BSED in terms of punctuality and attendance. There

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of Performance of Student Teachers in the in terms of Professional and Personal Characteristics

Performance Indicator	BEED			BSED		
	Weighted mean	SD	Description	Weighted Mean	SD	Description
1. Decisiveness	8	2	VS	8	1	VS
2. Honesty/Integrity	8	1	VS	8	1	VS
3. Dedication/Resourcefulness	8	1	VS	9	1	O
4. Initiative/Resourcefulness	8	1	VS	8	1	VS
5. Courtesy	8	6	VS	8	1	VS
6. Human Relations	8	1	VS	7	1	VS
7. Leadership	8	1	VS	8	1	VS
8. Stress tolerance	7.6	1.2	VS	7.6	1.2	VS
9. Fairness/Justice	7.7	1.2	VS	7.5	1.2	VS
10. Proper Attire/Good grooming	7.7	1.2	VS	9.3	1.2	O
Overall	7.9	0.18	VS	7.8	0.49	VS

Legend: 10 – 9 = Outstanding, 7 – 8 = Very Satisfactory, 5 – 6 = Satisfactory, 3 – 4 = Poor, 1- 2 = Needs Improvement

are three (3) performance indicators for this aspect and described as outstanding as the highest and needs improvement as the lowest.

From the table, it can be seen that BEED has a weighted mean of 7.9 which is described as very satisfactory and for BSED, the weighted mean is 7.8 which is described as very satisfactory. The result implies that both BEED and BSED student teachers are conscious of their punctuality and attendance to school and they are conscious the

importance of promptness in the submission of reports and other documents in school.

RESULTS

Table 6 presents the summary of the performance of BEED and BSED student teachers in the demonstration teaching during their deployment. There are three (3) components in the instruments used in evaluating demonstration teaching namely instructional competence,

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of Performance of Student Teachers in the in terms of Professional and Personal Characteristics

Performance Indicator	BEED			BSED		
	Weighted mean	SD	Description	Weighted Mean	SD	Description
1. Punctuality – number of times tardy during the period of practicum	7.83	1.02	VS	7.63	1.2	VS
2. Attendance – number of days absent during the period of practicum	7.8	0.9	VS	7.6	0.98	VS
3. Promptness in submission of required reports	7.9	1.04	VS	7.6	1.33	VS
Overall	7.9	0.18	VS	7.8	0.49	VS

Legend: 10 – 9 = Outstanding, 7 – 8 = Very Satisfactory, 5 – 6 = Satisfactory, 3 – 4 = Poor, 1- 2 = Needs Improvement

professional and personal characteristics, and punctuality and attendance.

From the table, it can be seen that no significant difference on the professional and personal characteristics of BEED and BSED student teachers in their performance in demonstration teaching. However, there is significant difference on the instructional competence and punctuality and attendance of BEED and BSED student teachers. This implies that the BEED and BSED have

common professional and personal characteristics such as being decisive, honest, dedicated, resourceful, courteous, and the like. They showed very satisfactory display of such professional and personal characteristics. On the other hand, there is felt difference between the BEED and BSED in terms of instructional competence and punctuality and attendance in terms of submission of reports and others documents. Perhaps, such difference is attributed to the academic environment, exposure and

Table 6: Summary Table for Test of Significant Difference of BEED and BSED student teachers in their Performance in the Demonstration Teaching

Aspects	t-value	df	p-value
Instructional Competence	2.915524*	21	0.008269
Professional and Personal Characteristics	0.632886 ns	9	0.542552
Punctuality and Attendance	7.46203*	2	.000862

Legend: * = significant at 0.05 level ($p < 0.05$), ** = highly significant at 0.05 level ($p < 0.05$), ns = not significant at 0.05 level

other factors like resources in addressing the instructional competence and punctuality and attendance of student teachers.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are considered:

1. The student teachers both for BEED and BSED are within the age expected of them to be completing for the tertiary level of education. Mostly are female and have a very satisfactory academic performance.
2. The performance of BEED and BSED student teachers in demonstration teaching is very satisfactory in instructional competence, professional and personal characteristics, and attendance and punctuality.
3. The BEED and BSED student teachers displayed difference in terms professional and personal characteristics.

Recommendations

1. The profile of BEED and BSED student teachers should also consider variables such IQ and teaching aptitude test results.
2. The general weighted average should be categorized further under professional and general education.
3. The College should develop scheme of providing incentives for student teachers who are performing excellently on demonstration teaching.

4. The College should establish best practices in demonstration teaching.
5. The result can be a baseline for future improvement of experiential learning courses.

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